

20230710 fast analysis chloroplast and mitochondria *T. oceanica* in Fe limitation

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Analysis of complete and incomplete (but visible cells)

```
## [1] "D:/Users/Jhoanell/Documents/~Jhoanell 2025/Labo/Thalassiosira_project/~Thesis work/paper chloro"
```


rotype ○ To media ○ 100_rotype ○ Tp media ○ 100_

thylakoid ■ half ■ no ■ yes ■ N.

thylakoid ■ half ■ no ■ yes ■ N.

cristae half no yes NA

cristae half no yes N.

t_test for means

```
## # A tibble: 2 x 11
##   genotype .y.   group1 group2   n1   n2 statistic   df         p     p.adj
##   <fct>   <chr> <chr> <chr> <int> <int>   <dbl> <dbl>   <dbl>   <dbl>
## 1 To     bodies 100_Fe 5_Fe     17    11    -4.68  12.9  0.000437 4.37e-4
## 2 Tp     bodies 100_Fe 5_Fe      7     8     NaN   NaN   NaN       NaN
## # i 1 more variable: p.adj.signif <chr>
```



```
## # A tibble: 4 x 3
##   genotype media     n
##   <fct>    <fct> <int>
## 1 To      100_Fe    17
## 2 To      5_Fe     11
## 3 Tp      100_Fe     7
## 4 Tp      5_Fe     8
```


bodies 0 2 3 4

```
## # A tibble: 4 x 3
##   genotype media     n
##   <fct>    <fct> <int>
## 1 To      100_Fe    17
## 2 To      5_Fe     11
## 3 5_Fe    100_Fe     7
## 4 5_Fe     5_Fe     8
```


media ● 100_Fe ● 5_Fe genotype ● To ● Tp

media ◻ 100_Fe ◻ 5_Fe genotype ◻ To ◻ Tp